

Nutritious, safe and sustainable seafood for consumers of tomorrow

SEAFood^{TOMORROW} TQC Database

This database contains TQC-data (Traceability, Quality, Certification) generated during the development of Eco-Innovative products and solutions in the SEAFood^{TOMORROW} project.

All data contained within this database will be made available in Open Access at the end of the project.

Once registered, all users will be able to access and download data. Click the link below, complete the registration form and you will receive login details.

The database is managed by ILVO.

Link: <https://www.seafoodtomorrowdata.eu/tqc/Home/Login?returnurl=%2Ftqc%2F>

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